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GEOECOLOGICAL SITUATION OF MONO-CITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the geoecological situation of Uzbekistan monocities, existing problems, their features, and solutions.*

Keywords: *geoecological problem, human economic activity, extractive industry, oil refining, atmospheric pollution, building materials, solid waste.*

INTRODUCTION

Enter. Monocities differ from multifunctional cities by their composition, features of socio-economic development, the uniqueness of their geo-ecological situation, and in some cases, the urban economy has a serious negative impact on the environment. Consequently, the mono-city economy mainly specializes in the exploitation of mineral resources and the processing of mined raw materials, and these processes lead to significant changes in the lithological structure of the area, underground and underground waters, atmosphere, soil, flora, and fauna. Therefore, it is important to monitor the geoecological situation of monocities and to develop scientifically based proposals for improving the ecological situation based on the obtained data.

Purpose and tasks of work. The purpose of the work is to develop scientifically based proposals for improving the ecological situation in these settlements by analyzing the geoecological problems of the monocities of Uzbekistan. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

- assessment of the geoecological situation in these settlements using the data and other sources obtained during the sociological research conducted in narrowly specialized cities;
- division of monocities into groups according to the characteristics of environmental problems existing in them;
- justification of measures to eliminate environmental problems that have arisen in monocities.

The main part. The formation of the geoecological situation of the monocities of Uzbekistan is also characterized by which branch dominates the economy of these settlements, and most of the narrowly specialized cities of the republic must be formed based on extractive industry. On the other hand, the monocities formed based on the exploitation of fuel, ore, and non-ore mineral resources are very different from each other in terms of their features and their scale of impact on the environment. In addition, the environmental conditions of the developing monocities of the republic, which have arisen under the influence of factors such as processing industries, hydro-technical facilities, transport infrastructure, and recreational resources, have their characteristics.

According to the results of the socio-demographic research, the majority of respondents living in narrowly specialized cities related to the mining industry and thermal power plants consider the bad environmental situation to be one of the main problems (Figure 1). This indicator is equal to 95 % in the city of Kuvasay, 74 % in the city of Karaulbazar, 60 % in the town of Karatau, and 48 % in the towns of Shirin and Nurabad.

Figure 1. The percentage of respondents who included the bad environmental situation among the main problems in the monocity where they live (%)

The geocological situation in narrowly specialized cities of the republic can be analyzed based on the respondents' assessment of the ecological situation in the monocity where they live (Fig. 2). 80 % of respondents living in the city of Kuvasoy consider the environmental situation in this settlement to be unsatisfactory, this indicator is also much higher in the cities of Qarovulbazar (66 %), Shargun (65 %), and Karatau (62 %). In general, all respondents who live only in the city of Pitnak have a positive assessment of the environmental situation.

Figure 2. Respondents assessment of the environmental situation in the monocity where they live (%)

Based on the analysis of the data obtained during the research, it is possible to divide the monocities of the republic into several groups in terms of the composition of geocological problems, development characteristics, and relevance.

Monocities where a large amount of solid waste has accumulated in or near the urban area.

This category includes narrowly specialized cities formed based on ore mining and processing, such as Zarafshan, Uchkuduk, Muruntau, Zafarabad, Zarkent (Koshrobot district), Yangiabad, Krasnogorsk, Uygursay and a large amount of ore residues have accumulated in these settlements. It should be noted here that the percentage of most metals, especially gold, in the raw materials is very small, and the main part of the mined ores is turned into waste. Accumulation of these wastes causes the failure of agricultural lands, especially pastures. This situation is observed in monocities such as Zarafshan,

Muruntau and Zarkent (Koshrobot district), and the heaps of ore residues near these settlements are occupying increasingly large areas.

Among the solid via radioactive generated during uranium mining wastes are has particular importance, and their ecological danger is characterized by the fact that they can not only occupy useful lands but also seriously affect living organisms and, first of all, human health. According to information, the Uchkuduk district, which is the main uranium mining area of the republic, contains more than 3 million tons of uranium ore waste. Although it was formed based on the mining of uranium ore, the removal of radioactive waste around the city of Yangiabad and the town of Krasnogorsk, which completely stopped the activity of the city-forming enterprise since the end of the last century, has not yet been carried out. Today, an area of more than 50 square kilometers near the city of Yangiabad is occupied by radioactive waste with a total volume of 500 thousand m^3 , while in the territory of the city of Krasnogorsk, there is a total volume of uranium ore waste of more than 600 thousand m^3 .

Monocities with high atmospheric pollution with various harmful gases. This group includes narrowly specialized cities with a developed oil and gas processing industry, such as Karaulbazar, Tinchlik, Mubarak and Shurtan. For example, in the city of Karaulbazar, which is one of the largest centers of the countrys fuel and energy industry, as a result of the operation of the oil refinery, significant pollution of the atmosphere with various gases is observed in the city and its surrounding areas. The urgency of the problem of air pollution in the city of Karaulbazar is justified by the fact that the majority of respondents who took part in socio-demographic research assessed the environmental situation as unsatisfactory and included the bad environmental situation among the main problems in the city.

Monocities with a high level of atmospheric dust pollution. This category includes monocities like Kuvasay, Gazgan, Jumurtau, and Karatau, which mainly specialize in the production of building materials. Especially as a result of the activities of the Kuvasay building materials, which is the leader in cement production in the republic, significant pollution of the atmosphere of this city is observed.

Summary. It can be concluded from the analysis of the geoecological situation of monocities of the republic that there are various environmental problems in monocities that differ from each other in terms of economic specialization, and this situation should be taken into account when determining measures to eliminate existing environmental problems in the strategy of complex socio-economic development of narrowly specialized cities. For example, based on the experience of foreign countries, in monocities formed based on the exploitation of ore minerals and in the areas located near them, it is

possible to level the heaps of waste and build pastures, parks, or recreational landscapes. It should be emphasized that to protect nature and society from the effects of radioactive waste, it is necessary to establish measures to bury this waste underground in the prescribed manner in places far away from populated areas.

To improve the geo-ecological situation in cities such as Karaulbazar, Mubarak, and Tinchlik, where the level of atmospheric pollution with various harmful gases is high, it is required to update the existing air filters in the oil and gas processing enterprises operating in these settlements. Therefore, it is possible to achieve clean atmospheric air in monocities specializing in the oil and gas industry and the areas close to them. In addition, it is necessary to improve the ecological situation by implementing measures such as updating production technology and providing air filters in monocities with a high level of atmospheric dust pollution. It should be noted that it is important to regularly monitor air pollution in monocities whose geo-ecological situation is largely characterized by a high level of air pollution.

As mentioned above, certain geo-ecological problems arise not only in the monocities of the republic formed based on the mining industry but also in narrowly specialized cities formed under the influence of other factors. For example, in monocities formed based on natural recreation resources, natural components are being damaged by the activities of vacationers, and the environment is becoming polluted with household waste. Therefore, regular monitoring of the ecological situation in each monocity, improvement of it, and development of measures to preserve the healthy state of the natural environment are among the urgent tasks.

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